

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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MUNDARIJA

Improving the efficiency of investment activity in oil and gas enterprises.....	24
Raxmatova M.G., G'ofurov Sh.N.	
Organization of control and evaluation of effectiveness in international companies.....	30
Nasimov Bakhtiyor Vasiyevich	
Xalqaro standartlarning korxonaga eksportini oshishidagi ahamiyati.....	35
Sobitov Diyor Abbralxonovich	
Erkin iqtisodiy zonalar boshqaruvining tashkiliy tuzilmasini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	40
Ataismatov Iqboljon Zumratjonovich	
Xorazm viloyatida turizm infratuzilmasini innovatsion rivojlantirish ko'rsatkichlarini ekonometrik modellashtirish va prognozlashtirishning ba'zi masalalari.....	46
Jumaniyazova Ro'za Quvondiq qizi	
Tijorat banklarining moliyaviy barqarorligini mustahkamlash.....	60
Rasulov Muxammad Bobur Fazliddin o'g'li	
Economic analysis of investment activity of enterprises.....	66
Shermatov Akhror Abduhakimovich	
Kichik biznesni rivojlantirishda innovatsion faoliyatni moliyalashtirish yo'nalishlari.....	72
Z. Rahimova	
Влияние углеродного следа на экологическую устойчивость узбекистана.....	76
Саттарова Барно Шухратовна	
Moliya bozori dastaklari orqali xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etish modellarining uslubiy asoslari.....	84
Ibragimov G'anijon G'ayratovich	
Maqsdadli tushumlarning audit obyekti sifatidagi tasnifi va tavsifi.....	90
Ne'matov Oybek Ismatullayevich, Qambarov Abduazizbek	
Bank majburiyatlari tushunchasi, uning mazmuni va mohiyati.....	96
Muminova Parvina Ilhom qizi	
Sanoat korxonalariga berilayotgan soliq imtiyozlari ma'murchiligini ta'minlash borasida amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar samaradorligi.....	100
Turabov Ulug'bek Olimjonovich	
Tur operatorlari va sayohat agentliklarida xarajatlar va foyda tahlili va uning turlari.....	106
Taniyev Ahmadjon Bahromovich	
O'zbekistonda kredit bozorini rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	113
Salimov Burxon Abubakirovich	
Social media marketing as a key strategy in modern business.....	125
Najimova Bakhtigul Abdilkasim qizi	
O'zbekistonda yashil mahsulotlar eksportini rivojlantirish orqali barqaror iqtisodiy o'sish va xalqaro integratsiyani ta'minlash.....	129
Radjabov Bunyod Abduxalilovich	
Оценка и управление рисками в проектах строительства энергетических объектов.....	136
Махматкулов Жамшед Бахтиёрович	
Iqtisodiyotda ko'chmas mulk bozori hamda uning xususiyatlari.....	140
Ibragimov Qobil To'xtamishovich, Raimkulov Sherali O'rozdavlatovich, G'ffarov Husayn Aliyor o'g'li, Ismoilov Davronjon Ilxomjon o'g'li, Tashpulatova Shaxnoza Tursunpulatovna	
Ekologik turizmning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ta'siri va uni rivojlantirish istiqbollari (Jizzax viloyati misolida).....	144
Isomiddinov Sherzod Sirojiddin o'g'li	
Ways to improve personnel policy in improving the quality of financial services provided by financial institutions.....	148
Ergashev Umidjon Ibragimovich	
Qo'shilgan qiymat solig'ining budjet daromadlarini shakllantirishdagi ahamiyati.....	152
Djabbarov Anvar Muxammadsaliyevich	

Tadbirkorlik subyektlarining barqarorlik reytingini aniqlash va ulardan samarali foydalanish yo'llari	157
Abdullayev Zafarbek Safibullayevich	
Tovar-moddiy zaxiralar auditini tashkil qilish masalalari	164
Turmanqulov Norpo'lat Sa'dullayevich, Botirov Lazizbek Botirovich	
O'zbekiston tijorat banklari faoliyatida aktivlar daromadligini oshirish masalalari.....	168
Saxibjonov Muzaffar Salijanovich	
Organization of control and evaluation of effectiveness in international companies.....	174
Nasimov Bakhtiyor Vasiyevich	
Strategic growth of global companies in contemporary environments.....	179
Djurabaev Otabek Djurabayevich	
Directions for management of the tax system.....	184
Sharokhmatov Abdurakhim Abdulamitovich	
Davlat korxonalarida moliyaviy samaradorlik va uni boshqarish tizimini takomillashtirish yo'nalishlari.....	188
Qarshiyev Nodirbek Olim o'g'li	
Проблемы, модели и методы оптимизации управления товарными запасами	193
Бабаджанов Шопулат Шомашрабович	
Literature review: the significance of digitization to management credit activity of commercial banks	200
Jo'rayev Eldor Berdibekovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasining davlat budjeti.....	205
Ajibaeva Raiya Maxsudovna	
Yashil iqtisodiyot kontsepsiyasining shakillanishi, taraqqiyot bosqichlari va uning dolzarbligi.....	212
Kodirov Javlonbek Nematullayevich	
Bank plastik kartalari orqali masofaviy xizmatlarni takomillashtirish.....	219
Abdullayeva Dildora Qudratovna, Abdullayev Baxodirjon Valijon o'g'li, Almuratova Nurliolmasoy Naim qizi	
O'zbekistonda iqtisodiy o'sishni ekonometrik modellashtirish	223
Shamsiyeva Feruza Muratxodjayevna	
Mahalla faoliyati ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlarini tahlil qilishning nazariy asoslari.....	232
Aliqulov Ravshan Shodiyor o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda lizing bozori tahlili.....	237
Boyev Bekzodjon Jo'raqul o'g'li, Shavkatov Behruz Rustam o'g'li	
Chakana savdoni rivojlantirishning mintaqaviy xususiyatlari	241
Ismoilov Shohjahon O'tkir o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda tibbiy xizmatlarning rivojlanish tendensiyalari, tarkibiy tuzilish tasnifi va marketing segmentlari	244
Axmedov Zafarjon A'zamovich	
Мировой опыт и перспективы развития свободно экономических зон в Республике Узбекистан.....	250
Кадирова Истора Кадирова	
Перспективы реформирования налоговой системы Республики Узбекистан в условиях глобализации.....	254
Буранова Лола Вахобовна, Садилов Искандар Гайратович	
O'zbekiston 2030 strategiyasi – islohotlar tizimligida ipoteka kreditining dolzarbligi.....	263
A'zamxo'jayeva Nihola	
O'zbekistonda sug'urta mexanizmlarini rivojlantirish istiqbollari	267
Shoraximova Zilola Nosirdjanovna	
Biologiya va tibbiyotda matematik statistika	271
Voxidov Alikul Melitoshevich	
Viloyatda chorvachilik mahsulotlarini o'tgan yilga nisbatan o'zgarishi.....	283
Azimov Allaberdin O'rinovich, Begaliyeva Madina Abdusamatovna	
Servis korxonalarida mobil ilovalar yordamida interaktiv xizmatlar yaratish	289
Ne'matov Nizom Ismatullayevich	
Oziq-ovqat ta'minot zanjiri tushunchasi va uning zamonaviy tendensiyalari.....	293
Nazarova A.N	

Влияние искусственного интеллекта при разработке стратегических программ на экономическое развитие страны.....	300
Каримова Нуржахон Олим кизи	
Kichik va o'rta biznesda moliyaviy menejment: muammolar va yechimlar	306
Saidvaliyeva Nigora Ziyodillayevna	
Теоретико-правовая характеристика экономических отношений	313
Фарход Махмудович Тиркашев, Исломжон Жамшедович Жамшедов	
Cash flow reporting in Uzbekistan: national accounting standards and international standards application	318
Ochilov Ilyos Keldiyorovich	
Tadbirkorlik salohiyatini rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari va takomillashtirish mexanizmlari	324
Baxtiyor Xabibullayev Abdulvoxid o'g'li	
Получение долгосрочного кредита и определение его размера для привлечения лизинга	330
Латипова Шахноза Махмудовна	
Ko'chmas mulk solig'ining ko'chmas mulk bozori tendensiyalariga ta'siri	335
To'lakov Ulug'bek Toshmamatovich	
Rivojlangan mamlakatlarning davlat qarzi va uni boshqarishdagi tajribasini tahlil qilishga ilmiy yondashuv	343
Suyunov Dilmurod Xolmuradovich, Abdurahmonova Feruzabonu	
Эффективный инновационный менеджмент в системе здравоохранения Республики Узбекистан.....	353
Абдурахманов З.М.	
Islom moliyasining O'zbekistondagi o'rni va O'zbekiston Respublikasining islomiy tashkilotlar va banklar bilan aloqasi	356
Otajonova Charosxon Polvonquli qizi, Elboyev Otajon Polvonquliyevich	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlarida innovatsion faoliyatni rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari.....	361
Oxunjonova Madina Isoqjonovna	
Основные задачи обеспечения цифровой информационной безопасности в образовательном процессе	365
Иззатилла Пулатов Кудратиллаевич	
Tijorat banklarida komplaens nazoratni takomillashtirish.....	373
Muminova Marguba Mamirkulovna	
Kichik biznes uchun soliq imtiyozlari va ularning samaradorligi.....	378
Sarvar Ochilov	
Xalqaro moliyaviy tashkilotlarning davlat iqtisodiy rivojlanishidagi o'rni.....	387
Raxmonova Dildora Ergash qizi	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida kreditning iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishdagi o'rni	395
Eshqobulova Charos O'roq qizi	
Mintaqa sanoat korxonalarida investitsiya jarayonlari rivojlanish tendensiyasining statistik tahlili.....	399
Quvatova Gulzoda Faxriddin qizi	
Natijalarga yo'naltirilgan budjetlashtirish samarali budjet menejmentining omili sifatida	403
N. Sheraliev	
O'zbekistonda kichik biznesning rivojlanish tendensiyalari va istiqbollari	408
Salayev Jasurbek Komilovich	
Features and prospects for the development of digital marketing in Uzbekistan.....	414
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
Анализ динамики импорта узбекистана в 2017–2024 годах с учетом индекса сложности продукции (PCI)	418
Жабборова Нодира Холмурод кизи	
O'zbekistonning kredit riskini baholash: iqtisodiy barqarorlik va xavf omillari tahlili	422
Hakimov Hakimjon Abdullo o'g'li	
Investitsion jozibadorlikni oshirish – korxonalarining raqobatbardoshligini oshirishning muhim shartidir	426
Karimova Dilafuz Sadirdin qizi	

Sanoat korxonalarida innovatsion faollikni oshirish omillari.....	431
Qo'ziyev Shodiyor Qilichboy o'g'li, Xakimov Javohir Hamza o'g'li, Turganbaev Nursultan Bayram o'g'li, Masharipov Rasulbek Jo'rabekovich, Xasanov Ruslan Raxmatovich, Nurullayev Jasurbek Davronbekovich	
Теоретические основы формирования понятия «финансовая стабильность».....	437
Алиева Сусанна Сейрановна	
Developing the labor market and strategies for reducing unemployment.....	442
Tojiyeva Muhabbatxon Mansurjon qizi, Elmurodov Mukhammadkodir Nurmuhammad	
Iqlim o'zgarishi sharoitida raqamli texnologiyalar orqali qishloq xo'jaligida samaradorlikni oshirish yo'llari.....	450
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Ochilov Ilhom Sayitqulovich, Sayfullayeva Ruxshona Farrux qizi	
To'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalarning sanoatni rivojlantirishdagi roli.....	458
Samijonov Musobek G'ayratjon o'g'li	
Ishlab chiqarish korxonalarida risklarni boshqarishning asosiy yo'nalishlari va rivojlanish istiqbollari.....	466
Muxitdinov Shuhrat Ziyavitdinovich	
Ovqatlanish xizmatlarini rivojlantirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlaridan foydalanish va samaradorligini oshirishning asosiy yo'nalishlari.....	470
Ravshanov Zaxiriddin Ibragimovich	
Ta'lim jarayonida sun'iy intellektdan foydalanishning ahamiyati.....	477
Safayeva Dilafruz Ruzmatovna, Karimov Abrorjon Shavkat o'g'li	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarini xarajatlarini rejalashtirish va moliyalashtirish: amaldagi holat tahlili.....	482
Bauyetdinov M.J., Medetbayeva D.T	
Tijorat banklarida foiz risklarini baholash va boshqarish.....	487
Karimov Mardon Akram o'g'li	
Zamonaviy sharoitda bank innovatsiyalaridan foydalanishning istiqbolli yo'nalishlari.....	494
Xodjimamedov Akmal Ashurovich	
A local perspective on sustainable supply chain management in Uzbekistan.....	501
Oybek Rafukjonkhajiev	
Raqamli texnologiyalar orqali sug'urta kompaniyalar marketing faoliyatini takomillashtirish.....	505
Rashidova Dildora Rasul qizi	
O'zbekistonning strategik rivojlanish davrida investitsiyalarning o'rni.....	511
Akbaraliyeva Aziza Maxmadali qizi	
O'zbekiston media bozori: rivojlanishi va afzalliklari.....	516
Qodirov Obidjon Olim o'g'li	
Порядок учета скидок в бухгалтерском учете на основе МСФО.....	520
Камолова Феруза Кахрамоновна	
Tijorat banklari transformatsiyasini amalga oshirishda qimmatli qog'ozlar bozorida foydalanishning xorijiy tajribasi.....	525
Bobur Abrorovich Yusupov	
Neft va gaz sanoati korxonalarini resurslardan samarali foydalanishning xorijiy tajribalari tahlili.....	533
Sonayev Sanjar Nurmatovich	
Оценка социально-экономического воздействия железнодорожных проектов.....	539
Хужаяров Бекзод Баходир угли	
Rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlarda islom mikromoliyalashning innovatsion mexanizmlari va xalqaro tajriba.....	544
Sharipova Maxliyoxon Baxtiyor qizi	
Iqtisodiy samaradorlik tushunchasining ilmiy- nazariy tahlili.....	548
Ibragimov Zukhriddin Sayfutdinovich	
Ipoteka kreditlarini moliyalashtirishda banklarning o'rni va istiqbollari.....	552
Muhitdinov Ulug'bek Diyorovich	
Mintaqaviy mehnat bozorini shakllanishining shart-sharoitlari, omillari, o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va prinsiplari.....	556
Amonov Navro'zxon Saloxiddin o'g'li	
Development of digital marketing for sustainable tourism development in Uzbekistan.....	560
Nasibabonu Abdurakhmonovna Akramova	

Kichik biznes subyektlarining raqobatbardoshligini oshirishga qaratilgan innovatsion yondashuvlar	565
Ibragimov Ulmas	
Tijorat banklarining moliyaviy xavfsizligini ta'minlashning dolzarb masalalari	569
Akbarov Behzodxon Ulug'bek o'g'li	
Amerika qo'shma shtatlarida federal zaxira tizimi tomonidan amalga oshirilgan noan'anaviy pul-kredit siyosati.....	574
Djumonov Dilshod Safaroliyevich	
Intellectual mulkning ishlab chiqarishdagi ahamiyati	581
Farhod Mahmudovich Tirkashyev, Azizbek Umid o'g'li Abduvaliyev	
Tijorat banklari moliyaviy barqarorligini baholashning xorijiy davlatlar tajribasi	585
Sattarova Gulshan Muxiddinovna	
Qimmatli qog'ozlar bozorida moliyaviy xavfsizlik: investorlar misolida.....	589
Boysunov Jamshid Baxriddin ug'li	
Amaliy-ilmiy tadqiqotlarning mazmuni, asosiy maqsadlari va qo'llanilish shakllari.....	593
Raupov Jamshid Rashidovich, Kaxramonov Zafar Kaxramonovich	
Tijorat banklarida korporativ boshqaruvni takomillashtirishning dolzarb masalalari.....	597
Ergashev Olim Kenjayevich	
Islom darchalari asosida moliyalashtirishni joriy etish istiqbollari	602
Gulyamova Shaxnoza Gafurdjanovna	
Влияние финансовых технологий на трансформацию страхового рынка.....	606
Тангирбердиева Гулчехра Рахимжановна	
Tadbirkorlik faoliyatini rivojlanishida mamlakatimiz iqtisodiyotini holati tahlili	611
Muradova Maxliyoxon Ravshanovna	
Foreign experience in the formation of banking assets in improving the efficiency of the activities of commercial banks.....	615
Ibrohimov Davronbek Muhammadi ogli	
Роль и значение экономического потенциала в формировании стратегии регионов Узбекистана.....	628
Абдалова З.Т.	
Перспективы развития торговых отношений между Китаем и Узбекистаном.....	634
Фазлиддинова Шахруза студентка, Расулев Дильмурод Мирза-Ахмедович	
Korxonalarda moliyaviy instrumentlarning hisobi va audit masalalarini rivojlantirish	640
Maxmudov Saidjamol Kadirjanovich	
Barqaror ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari.....	647
Rajabov Alibek	
Digital technologies as a driver for the development of mice tourism in Uzbekistan	654
Ilkhomova Gulnoza Zaynitdin qizi	

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AS A DRIVER FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF MICE TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article examines the role of contemporary digital technologies in the MICE tourism industry of Uzbekistan and their impact on enhancing the cultural attractiveness of events. The study analyzes technologies such as virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR), artificial intelligence (AI), and online event booking and management platforms. It evaluates the current level of digital infrastructure in Uzbekistan, identifies existing obstacles, and highlights potential avenues for the sector's digital transformation. The analysis indicates that uneven development of digital infrastructure across regions represents the primary challenge, while VR/AR technologies show the highest potential for creating immersive cultural programs. The article provides recommendations for stimulating digital transformation in Uzbekistan's MICE tourism, considering the country's cultural specifics and addressing identified barriers, including targeted financial programs and educational initiatives.

Key words: MICE tourism, digital technologies, virtual reality, augmented reality, artificial intelligence, cultural heritage, digital infrastructure, Uzbekistan.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola O'zbekistonning MICE turizm sanoatida zamonaviy raqamli texnologiyalarning o'rni va ularning tadbirlarning madaniy jozibadorligini oshirishga ta'sirini ko'rib chiqadi. Tadqiqot virtual va kengaytirilgan haqiqat (VR/AR), sun'iy intellekt (AI) va onlayn tadbirlarni bron qilish va boshqarish platformalari kabi texnologiyalarni tahlil qiladi. U O'zbekistondagi raqamli infratuzilmaning hozirgi darajasini baholaydi, mavjud to'siqlarni aniqlaydi va sektorni raqamli transformatsiya qilishning potentsial yo'llarini ko'rsatadi. Tahlil shuni ko'rsatadiki, mintaqalar bo'ylab raqamli infratuzilmaning notekis rivojlanishi asosiy muammo hisoblanadi, VR/AR texnologiyalari esa immersiv madaniy dasturlarni yaratish uchun eng yuqori salohiyatni ko'rsatadi. Maqolada O'zbekistonning MICE turizmida raqamli transformatsiyani rag'batlantirish, mamlakatning madaniy xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda va aniqlangan to'siqlarni, jumladan, maqsadli moliyaviy dasturlar va ta'lim tashabbuslarini bartaraf etish bo'yicha tavsiyalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: MICE turizmi, raqamli texnologiyalar, virtual haqiqat, kengaytirilgan haqiqat, sun'iy intellekt, madaniy meros, raqamli infratuzilma, O'zbekiston.

Аннотация: в статье исследуется роль современных цифровых технологий в индустрии MICE-туризма Узбекистана и их влияние на культурную привлекательность мероприятий. Проанализированы такие технологии, как виртуальная и дополненная реальность (VR/AR), искусственный интеллект (AI), онлайн-платформы бронирования и управления событиями. Рассматривается текущий уровень цифровой инфраструктуры в Узбекистане и её влияние на развитие MICE-туризма, а также выявляются препятствия и потенциальные направления развития цифровой трансформации отрасли. Анализ показал, что основной проблемой является неравномерность развития цифровой инфраструктуры в регионах, а наиболее перспективными технологиями – VR/AR для создания иммерсионных культурных программ. Представлены рекомендации по стимулированию цифровой трансформации MICE-туризма в Узбекистане, учитывающие культурную специфику страны и направленные на преодоление выявленных барьеров, включая создание целевых программ финансирования и образовательных инициатив.

Ключевые слова: MICE-туризм, цифровые технологии, виртуальная реальность, дополненная реальность, искусственный интеллект, культурное наследие, цифровая инфраструктура, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

The MICE (Meetings, Incentives, Conferences, Exhibitions) industry is among the fastest-growing sectors of tourism, significantly driven by innovations. On a global scale, digitalization is transforming how business events are planned and conducted, making them more interactive and efficient¹. The COVID-19 pandemic of 2020–2021 notably accelerated the adoption of digital solutions worldwide, revealing new opportunities for remote interactions².

In recent years, numerous studies have focused on digitalization within MICE tourism. Researchers such as A.A. Zhabarov³, M.A. Morozova, V.V. Fomina, and N.V. Zigern-Korn⁴ explore general trends in digital technology adoption within the event industry, highlighting the increasing importance of online platforms and hybrid event formats. In this context, integrating digital technologies provides new instruments for promoting Uzbekistan's rich cultural and historical heritage, which represents a significant resource for attracting MICE events.

Scholars such as R.Z. Alimutaev, L.S. Kryzhevich⁵, V.S. Bauer, and M.A. Kuznetsova [2] focus on specific technologies – virtual (VR), augmented (AR), mixed realities, and digital twin technology. A common theme in these studies is that such technologies are indispensable for innovative event design, enhancing audience engagement. Examples include virtual tours of Uzbekistan's historical sites conducted directly from the conference venue. Artificial intelligence (AI) applications, such as chatbots (M.M. Gasanguliyeva, V.E. Bayramova)⁶, recommendation systems (N.E. Valieva)⁷, and automated translation (N.K. Garbovsky, O.I. Kostikova)⁸, facilitate more personalized experiences for international visitors. Zh.A. Kiprushina examines online platforms and mobile apps as integral parts of MICE, facilitating participant interaction, feedback collection, and convenient access to cultural information⁹. S.D. Serdyukov elaborates on the role of big data analytics in personalizing tourism services¹⁰, highlighting its relevance to the cultural dimension of events.

Nonetheless, most research focuses on developed countries (Europe, the USA, and Southeast Asia). The integration of digital technologies in MICE tourism within developing countries with rich cultural heritage, such as Uzbekistan, remains insufficiently studied. Uzbek scholars like O.K. Khurramov¹¹, N.B. Atamuratova¹², and S.S. Gulyamov, A.T. Shermukhamedov, and M.H. Mukhitdinova¹³ have offered descriptive rather than comprehensive analyses of the challenges and opportunities of digitalization specific to Uzbekistan.

Thus, this study aims to analyze how modern digital technologies can integrate into Uzbekistan's MICE tourism, explore the opportunities and prospects they open, and identify and systematize barriers to digital transformation in the industry.

The research objectives include addressing the following questions:

Which digital technologies have the highest potential for integration into Uzbekistan's MICE tourism, considering its unique cultural heritage?

What are the main barriers impeding digital transformation in Uzbekistan's MICE industry?

Which governmental support measures and private-sector initiatives can most effectively stimulate the adoption of digital technologies in Uzbekistan's MICE tourism?

To achieve the stated goal and answer these questions, the following methodology was developed:

- 1 Top MICE Industry Latest Trends in 2024 // MICE Magazine. Available at: <https://www.micemag.com/top-mice-industry-latest-trends-in-2024/> (accessed: 09 March 2025). (In English)
- 2 Goeva, T. A., et al. The current state of MICE tourism in Russia // *Economics and Society*. – 2021. – No. 6-1 (85). – P. 561–564. (In Russian)
- 3 Жаберов А. А. Применение информационных технологий для повышения качества услуг Мисе-индустрии // *Экономика и региональное управление*. – 2017. – С. 448-451.
- 4 Морозова М. А., Фомина В. В., Зигерн-Корн Н. В. Новые тренды в индустрии Мисе // *развитие современной экономики: актуальные вопросы теории и практики*. – 2022. – С. 56-58.
- 5 Alimutaev, R. Z., Kryzhevich, L. S. The role of virtual and augmented reality in modern culture and entertainment // *Auditorium*. – 2024. – No. 1 (41). – P. 8–12. (In Russian)
- 6 Gassanguliyeva, M. M., Bayramova, V. E. Artificial intelligence technology used in digital management: Chatbot // *Endless Light in Science*. – 2023. – No. November. – P. 305–311. (In Russian)
- 7 Valieva, N. E. Recommendation systems in the tourism industry // *Information and Computer Technologies in the Economy, Education, and Social Sphere*. – Simferopol. – 2019. – No. 2. – P. 123–129. (In Russian)
- 8 Garbovsky, N. K., Kostikova, O. I. Intelligence for translation: Artificial or human? // *Moscow University Bulletin. Series 22. Theory of Translation*. – 2019. – No. 4. – P. 3–25. (In Russian)
- 9 Kiprushina, Zh. A. The use of mobile applications for coordinating tourist programs in MICE tourism // *Problems of the Development of the Tourism and Hospitality Industry: Experience and Innovations*. – 2018. – P. 135–141. (In Russian)
- 10 Serdyukov, S. D. Application of Big Data technology in the tourism industry: Critical analysis // *Professor's Journal. Series: Recreation and Tourism*. – 2022. – No. 2 (14). – P. 30–36. (In Russian)
- 11 Khurramov O. K. The highlight priorities for the development of digital tourism in Uzbekistan // *International scientific review*. – 2020. – №. LXIX. – С. 61-62.
- 12 Атамуратова Н. Б. Влияние информационных технологий на развитие туризма Узбекистана // *Бюллетень науки и практики*. – 2020. – Т. 6. – №. 12. – С. 297-305.
- 13 Гулямов С. С., Шермухамедов А. Т., Мухитдинова М. Х. Развитие искусственного интеллекта в Узбекистане // *Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali*. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 7-17.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

N. Ibromkhimov[3] studied the role of digital innovations in improving tourism experiences in Uzbekistan. Surveys of 500 travelers and 20 key stakeholders revealed the importance of technologies such as mobile apps, virtual reality (VR) and artificial intelligence (AI) in enhancing the experience, engagement and personalization of tourists. The results of the study show the need for strategic investments in technological infrastructure and digital literacy programs in the tourism sector of Uzbekistan.

“In the article, authors S. Gulyamov and others[4] analyzed the experience of developing digital technologies in Uzbekistan. The authors note that the country has five priorities: digital infrastructure, e-government, digital economy, national IT sector and IT education. As a result of the reforms carried out in these areas, Uzbekistan has made significant progress in introducing digital technologies.

The article authored by R. Ayupov and D. Boltaboyeva[5] describes the features and prospects of digital tourism development in Uzbekistan. The authors analyzed the importance of digital technologies in the field of tourism and indicated the necessary conditions and opportunities for the development of digital tourism in the country.

The article analyzes ways to effectively promote the MICE tourism potential of Uzbekistan. The author D. Boltaboyeva[6] shows the importance of MICE tourism in the country’s economy and defines the strategic goals and measures necessary for its development.

The role of digital technologies in the development of nostalgia tourism in Uzbekistan is studied in the article by N. Khamidova[7]. The author analyzes the possibilities of enriching nostalgia tourism experiences and attracting tourists with the help of digital technologies.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is based on an analysis of publicly available sources, including scholarly articles, industry reports, and statistical data. Sources were selected based on criteria such as publication within the last five years (2020–2025), peer-reviewed journals, authoritative industry publications, and relevance to key research terms.

A comparative approach was utilized, examining global trends in digital technology application in MICE tourism and contrasting them with Uzbekistan’s current situation. Kazakhstan (a Central Asian country with an emerging digital economy) and Georgia (a country with significant cultural heritage and active tourism development) were chosen for comparison. Key comparative parameters included internet penetration, governmental support programs for digital tourism, and examples of VR/AR integration.

Alongside the comparative analysis, the study examined examples of VR/AR and other technology implementations in cultural tourism. It also reviewed state policies and infrastructure projects in Uzbekistan related to tourism digitalization (digitization of cultural heritage sites, e-services for tourists) (Table 1).

Table 1. Comparative Analysis of Digitalization in MICE Tourism (Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Georgia)¹⁴.

Indicator	Uzbekistan	Kazakhstan	Georgia
Internet penetration (2023)	~76.6% [23]	~85.9% [29]	~80.5% [30]
Governmental digital tourism support	«Digital Uzbekistan 2030,» Cultural Heritage Platform, e-visa	«Digital Kazakhstan,» smart cities, IT-startups support in tourism	National Tourism Development Strategy, emphasis on online promotion, tourist-oriented digital platforms
Examples of VR/AR in MICE	3D museum exhibits, 3D Silk Road heritage tours, ongoing digitization initiatives	VR for presenting tourist sites at international exhibitions, selected VR-tour projects	Extensive AR use in tourist mobile apps (navigation, information), VR tours of historical sites (mainly in Tbilisi and Batumi)
Development of MICE infrastructure	New congress centers in Samarkand and Tashkent	Modern congress centers (Nur-Sultan, Almaty), uneven regional development	Infrastructure developing mainly in Tbilisi, Batumi; limited elsewhere

To identify primary barriers hindering digital transformation and to determine prospective development directions, an expert survey was conducted. The survey included 15 experts from the MICE industry, hotel businesses, and the Ministry of Tourism and Cultural Heritage of Uzbekistan. Results are summarized in Table 2.

14 compiled by the author

To identify barriers and drivers of digital transformation, an expert survey was conducted, involving 15 participants: five executives of MICE agencies, five hospitality industry representatives, and five officials from the Ministry of Tourism and Cultural Heritage of Uzbekistan. Data collection was conducted via anonymous online questionnaires using Google Forms, including closed-ended and open-ended questions. Analysis involved quantitative (frequency counting) and qualitative (interpretation of open-ended responses) approaches.

Expert survey results indicate that infrastructural, financial, human resource, and informational factors constitute the primary barriers to the digital transformation of MICE tourism in Uzbekistan (Table 2).

Table 2. Factors Hindering Digital Transformation of MICE Tourism in Uzbekistan and Their Causes¹⁵.

Factor	% of experts noting the factor	Causes
Uneven development of digital infrastructure	80%	Priority given to major cities; insufficient attention to regional areas.
Limited financial resources and investment	73%	General economic level, investment priorities, lack of targeted funding programs.
Lack of digital skills among personnel	67%	Weaknesses in educational systems, lack of specialized training programs.
Language and content barriers	53%	Predominance of English-language content and software, lack of localized solutions.
Cybersecurity concerns and trust issues	47%	Risks associated with data security and cybercrime; insufficient awareness of security measures.
Low awareness and demand among customers	40%	Weak marketing of digital MICE opportunities; insufficient awareness of the advantages offered by digital technologies.

To contextualize Uzbekistan's position in the regional landscape of digital MICE tourism development, a comparative analysis was conducted with Kazakhstan and Georgia – countries with similar initial conditions (developing economies, rich cultural heritage, and tourism focus). The results, presented in Table 1, indicate that Uzbekistan is comparable to Kazakhstan and Georgia regarding key digitalization indicators. However, there are differences in governmental policies and examples of specific technology implementations. Kazakhstan emphasizes developing smart cities and supporting IT startups, while Georgia focuses on online promotion and AR technology integration into mobile apps. Uzbekistan actively digitizes cultural heritage sites.

Methodologically, the research included analysis and synthesis of literature, statistical data collection (internet penetration, use of digital services; data from 2021–2024 reports by DataReportal and official Uzbek statistics), and expert analysis. Validity was ensured by using multiple data sources and triangulation of methods (literature, statistics, expert assessments). Reliability was ensured through detailed procedural descriptions, facilitating reproducibility.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Uzbekistan has undertaken substantial steps toward integrating digital technologies within the Meetings, Incentives, Conferences, and Exhibitions (MICE) industry. The “Digital Uzbekistan 2030” strategy, approved by Presidential Decree No. UP-6079 on October 5, 2020¹⁶, aims to accelerate digital economic development and extensively introduce advanced information and communication technologies across all sectors, including the MICE industry.

In 2022, the multi-year international project “3D Digital Silk Road” was completed. This project was coordinated by E. Milos from the Lublin University of Technology (LUT), Poland, and Uzbek researchers D. Mukhamedova, R. Kayumov, B. Yeshchanov, and U. Abdullaev¹⁷. The project digitally recreated cultural heritage sites along the Great Silk Road, including mosques, mausoleums, minarets, and madrassas in Samarkand, Tashkent, Khiva, and Bukhara¹⁸. Additionally, 3D models of museum exhibits, such as ceramics from Afrasiab¹⁹,

¹⁵ compiled by the author

¹⁶ Президент Республики Узбекистан. Об утверждении Стратегии «Цифровой Узбекистан-2030» и мерах по ее эффективной реализации: Указ Президента Республики Узбекистан от 5 октября 2020 г. № УП-6079 1 // Национальная база данных законодательства Республики Узбекистан. URL: <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/5031048> (дата обращения: 9 марта 2025 г.).

¹⁷ 3D Digital Silk Road // Информация о проекте. URL: https://silkroad3d.com/?page_id=1113&lang=ru (дата обращения: 10.03.2025).

¹⁸ 3D Digital Silk Road // Мавзолей Гур-Эмир. URL: https://silkroad3d.com/?page_id=285&lang=ru (дата обращения: 11.03.2025).

¹⁹ 3D Digital Silk Road // Самарканд 3D модели музейных экспонатов. URL: https://silkroad3d.com/?page_id=488&lang=ru (дата обращения: 11.03.2025).

and virtual museum tours were created. These 3D tours can be utilized by MICE event organizers to provide participants with preliminary cultural experiences and supplementary activities during conferences and exhibitions.

In October 2024, Uzbekistan adopted the “Strategy for the Development of Artificial Intelligence Technologies until 2030”²⁰. Currently, over 20 AI-based projects have been implemented, and approximately 70 more are in development for various industries and major enterprises. Uzbekistan’s international ranking in the AI Readiness Index has improved by 17 positions²¹.

A unified digital platform connecting cultural heritage sites²², supported by relevant government resolutions²³, facilitates virtual access to cultural resources prior to events, enabling participants to explore landmarks and museums through online tours and 3D models. During events, technologies enrich the content by introducing interactive elements such as AR applications that animate exhibits or VR reconstructions of historical events. Digitalization also supports the preservation and dissemination of cultural content: artistic performances, artisan workshops, and other cultural activities can be recorded and shared digitally, ensuring long-term cultural impact. Personalization of cultural experiences is possible through data analysis and AI, helping match cultural programs to participant preferences. Furthermore, digital technologies expand the audience of MICE events through virtual and hybrid formats, making Uzbekistan’s cultural heritage accessible to global participants.

Digital Infrastructure in Uzbekistan and its Influence on MICE Tourism.

Internet penetration and connectivity: As of early 2023, approximately 76.6% of Uzbekistan’s population had internet access²⁴, exceeding the global average (~64%). The number of active mobile SIM cards reached around 31.8 million (91% of the population). Major cities have access to 4G networks, and initiatives to deploy 5G are ongoing.

Electronic governmental tourism services: Uzbekistan has introduced a visa-free regime for citizens from 101 countries and established an e-visa system²⁵.

Digital tourism projects: A unified cultural heritage digital platform has been launched, complemented by online maps, mobile guides, and the official tourism portal Uzbekistan.travel.

Conference halls and technical facilities: Uzbekistan has constructed and modernized congress centers, such as the International Congress Center in Samarkand²⁶ and the “Tashkent City” Congress Hall²⁷.

Human capital and IT ecosystem: Uzbekistan hosts an IT Park in Tashkent²⁸, and universities are actively preparing IT specialists²⁹.

The results illustrate considerable potential for digital technologies to enhance MICE tourism in Uzbekistan, particularly in terms of enriching the cultural component of events. Comparative analysis with Kazakhstan and Georgia (Table 1) indicates that, despite similar internet penetration rates and governmental initiatives, Uzbekistan lags in regional infrastructure development, identified as a key barrier (Table 2).

Findings address the research objectives as follows: First, VR/AR technologies emerge as most promising, offering immersive cultural heritage presentations essential for international audiences. Second, primary

20 Постановление Президента Республики Узбекистан от 14 октября 2024 г. № ПП-358 «Об утверждении Стратегии развития технологий искусственного интеллекта до 2030 года» [Электронный ресурс]. — Ташкент, 2024. — Режим доступа: <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/7158606> (дата обращения: 11.03.2025).

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